

Heritage — Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey Bibliography

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April 3, 2025

The *Heritage — Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey* (H-SeTIS) database is a comprehensive survey of semantic and interoperable resources within the Heritage domain. It includes records for five key resource types: four categories of semantic artefacts—**ontologies**, **metadata standards**, **thesauri**, and **application profiles**—as well as **software tools** that implement these semantic artefacts. A **semantic artefact** is defined as «a machine-actionable and -readable formalization of a conceptualization, enabling sharing and reuse by both humans and machines» (Hugo et al. 2020). The development and structure of H-SeTIS are described in detail in Scarpa and Valente 2024a.

The database includes a **curated bibliography** that gathers **relevant literature** connected to the records in H-SeTIS, as well as **general resources** valuable for semantic web development in the Heritage field. This bibliography is available on [H-SeTIS](#) and maintained via Zotero and is accessible as a [public group](#). Each record has been reviewed to ensure compliance with **FAIR standards**, and unique identifiers (such as ISBN, DOI, or URL) have been included when available. **This PDF** document has been compiled from the H-SeTIS Zotero library using \LaTeX and BibTeX. The code is available in a dedicated [GitLab repository](#).

This activity was carried out by Erica Scarpa and Riccardo Valente of the CNR-ISPC, Milan branch, within Activity 4.10 of the H2IOSC Project (H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – NRRP M4C2 - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005; h2iosc.cnr.it).

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Scarpa, E. and Valente, R. (2024), *Heritage — Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey Bibliography*. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.15132745](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15132745)

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